

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

DIGITIZATION AS A PLATFORM FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE VOCATIONAL EDUCATION SYSTEM IN THE KYRGYZ REPUBLIC

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ABSTRACT

The article examines trends in the development of the education sector of the Kyrgyz Republic in the context of digitalization. The purpose of the study is a comprehensive analysis of the dynamics of development indicators of vocational education organizations at both the secondary and higher levels and the state of digitalization of the educational sector. Digitalization of vocational education is becoming part of the state strategy for the development of the education sector and the economy as a whole. Digital technologies contribute to the creation of virtual educational platforms for distance education and use throughout the educational process to improve the quality of educational services.

Keywords: educational organizations of secondary vocational education, digitalization, educational organizations of higher vocational education, number of students, number of personal computers in organizations of higher and secondary vocational education.

Introduction

The education sector is the dominant factor in the formation of human capital as a set of physical, intellectual and spiritual components of the population of any country. The formation of human capital in terms of acquiring knowledge, skills, and necessary competencies for participation in social production is ensured by the education sector. In the context of globalization and involvement in world economic relations, it is necessary to correspond to the level of development of human capital in developed countries to ensure the competitiveness of the national economy [1]. The rapid development of new technologies and the generation of new knowledge in the global space requires mastering them in order to be involved in the global economy and create partnership economic relations. The education sector acts as a platform for interaction of all stakeholders to acquire the skills, knowledge, and competencies necessary to participate in social production and provide benefits to society. Highly skilled human capital becomes the driving force of innovation and economic development. Education, regardless of age, helps people adapt to rapidly changing conditions in technology and labor market requirements, achieve professional heights and build a career trajectory in accordance with their capabilities and life goals. Based on the above, we conclude that the role of education in the national economy and increasing its competitiveness is high and undeniable. In addition, the education sector is a driver for

the development of other industries. Therefore, an analysis of the education development system is necessary to identify problems and determine priority directions for its development [3].

Digitalization as a trend that has covered all aspects of human life almost all over the world has turned out to be a key factor in improving communications between participants in the educational process and creating new teaching methods. The Kyrgyz Republic also strives to achieve complete digitalization of the educational sector to improve the quality of educational services and the competitiveness of the national education system [2].

During the research process, quantitative methods were used to analyze statistical information on indicators of the development of vocational education organizations at both the secondary and higher levels and the state of digitalization of the educational sector, which made it possible to assess trends in its development. To analyze statistical information, statistical research methods were used, such as constructing a grouping of statistical data, constructing time series, graphical methods for presenting time series and their analysis [4].

Results

During 2018-2022, the number of educational organizations of secondary vocational education of state ownership decreased by 16 units and in 2022 amounted

to 98 units [7]. On the contrary, the number of educational institutions of higher professional education of state ownership increased by 9 units (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dynamics of the number of educational organizations of state ownership in the Kyrgyz Republic for 2018-2022, units

Source: compiled according to data from the National Statistics Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic [7]

During 2018-2022, the number of educational organizations of secondary vocational education of private ownership increased by 10 units and in 2022 amounted to 98 units [7]. The number of educational

institutions of higher professional education of private ownership changed slightly, increasing by 1 unit (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Dynamics of the number of educational organizations of private ownership in the Kyrgyz Republic for 2018-2022, units

Source: compiled according to data from the National Statistics Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic [7]

Analysis of the dynamics of the number of students in state educational institutions of secondary vocational education in the Kyrgyz Republic for 2018-2022 allowed us to determine an increase of 13.7%. So,

in 2022 it amounted to 90,204 people versus 79,364 people in 2018 [7].

An analysis of the dynamics of the number of students in state educational organizations of higher professional education in the Kyrgyz Republic for 2018-

2022 revealed an increase of 38.4%. Thus, in 2022 it amounted to 195,522 people versus 141,223 people in 2018 [7] (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Dynamics of the number of students in state educational organizations of secondary and higher vocational education in the Kyrgyz Republic for 2018-2022, people

Source: compiled according to data from the National Statistics Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic [7]

An analysis of the dynamics of the number of students in private educational institutions of secondary vocational education in the Kyrgyz Republic for 2018-2022 allowed us to determine a significant increase of 47.7% in contrast to the increase in the number of students in state educational organizations. So, in 2022 it amounted to 17,982 people versus 12,171 people in 2018 [7].

An analysis of the dynamics of the number of students in private educational institutions of higher professional education in the Kyrgyz Republic for 2018-2022 revealed an increase of 37.2%. Thus, in 2022 it amounted to 32,060 people versus 23,362 people in 2018 [7] (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Dynamics of the number of students in private educational institutions of secondary and higher vocational education in the Kyrgyz Republic for 2018-2022, people

Source: compiled according to data from the National Statistics Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic [7]

Digitalization of professional education improves the quality of educational services, contributes to the development of relevant competencies among students and depends largely on the technical equipment of the educational process [9].

An analysis of the dynamics for 2018-2022 of the number of personal computers in organizations of higher professional education of the Kyrgyz Republic used for educational purposes showed an increase of

91.2%. Thus, in 2022 it amounted to 31,006 units versus 16,219 units in 2018 [7].

In turn, an analysis of the dynamics for 2018-2022 of the number of personal computers in secondary vocational education organizations of the Kyrgyz Republic used for educational purposes showed an increase of 26.6%. So, in 2022 it amounted to 7936 units versus 6269 units in 2018 [7] (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Dynamics of the number of personal computers in organizations of higher and secondary vocational education of the Kyrgyz Republic, used for educational purposes for 2018-2022, units

Source: compiled according to data from the National Statistics Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic [7]

This positive trend reflects the management’s attention to improving the quality of educational services and the desire to bring the level of graduates’ training into line with the requirements of employers and the labor market. This trend is confirmed by such relative indicators as the number of personal computers used for educational purposes per organization and per 1000 students.

If we present a statistical series of indicators for 2018-2022, we can state that in organizations of higher professional education of the Kyrgyz Republic, the number of personal computers used for educational purposes per organization increased by 190 units or by 59.7%, while the number personal computers used for educational purposes per 1000 students increased by 86 units or 60.6% [7] (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Dynamics of the number of personal computers used for educational purposes in organizations of higher professional education of the Kyrgyz Republic, units

Source: compiled according to data from the National Statistics Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic [7]

Similarly, let’s analyze the number of personal computers in organizations of secondary vocational education of the Kyrgyz Republic, used for educational

purposes per organization, it can be noted that in 2018-2022, which did not increase so significantly, by only 14 units or 33.3 % [7] (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Dynamics of the number of personal computers used for educational purposes in organizations of higher professional education of the Kyrgyz Republic, units

Source: compiled according to data from the National Statistics Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic [7]

While the number of personal computers used for educational purposes per 1000 students increased by 17 units or 20.7% [7].

Conclusion

The development of the education sector of the Kyrgyz Republic is an integration process into the global educational space. Involving foreign partners in the creation of joint educational programs, participation in international educational projects, trainings, courses contributed to joining the Bologna process and adaptation in the structure and content of the main educational programs of bachelor's, master's, and PhD programs.

Digitalization of vocational education is becoming part of the state strategy for the development of the education sector and the economy as a whole. Digital technologies contribute to the creation of virtual educational platforms for distance education, which is becoming relevant and in demand. In addition, conducting online lectures and courses increases accessibility and provides time flexibility in learning [8].

Accessing the Internet and using the latest information and communication technologies allows you to find partners abroad. In addition, the increase in the number of educational organizations in the Kyrgyz Republic is a prerequisite for the recognition of educational programs in other countries. This factor allowed educational organizations of the Kyrgyz Republic to enter the international educational market and attract foreign students [6]. This is a trend in the development of educational organizations, increasing the motivation of teachers to improve their professional level, including language training. English as a language of international communication has become a key point for the development of educational programs for foreigners. The quality of specialist training has increased and was supported by positive feedback from graduates and employers of graduates, which will further serve as advertising and a means of promoting educational services abroad [5].

Thus, the development of education based on the digitalization of management processes of educational organizations, the processes of interaction of all subjects of educational services is a factor in the innovative

development of the economy, increasing its economic growth, reducing labor migration, increasing the standard of living of the population, and overcoming poverty of the population.

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